

Life history and plant host range of the rice green semilooper

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We used a greenhouse mass-rearing technique to study the life history of the rice green semilooper *Naranga aenescens* Moore. Development from egg to adult takes 18-21 d. Eggs are laid either singly or in clusters of 2-13 and hatch in 3-4 d. Larvae undergo 5 instars over 12-13 d, pupation takes 3-4 d, and adult moths live 5-6 d.

Of the 19 plant species tested, *Leersia hexandra* and *Echinochloa indica* were equally suitable to rice as hosts, but more eggs were laid on rice in a no-choice test (see table). Complete egg-to-adult development but low survival occurred on *Cyperus diffusus*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *Paspalum paspalodes*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Echinochloa colona*, and sorghum. Larvae died during the first and second stadia in *Cyperus diffusus*, *Echinochloa*

Comparison of 16 weed and 3 crop species as *Naranga aenescens* host.^a

Plant species	Eggs laid ^b (no./female)	Larval development (d)	Pupal development (d)	Egg-to-adult survival (%)
<i>Oryza sativa</i> (rice)	454 a	14 a	4.3 ab	44 a
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	66 bcde	13 a	4.3 ab	56 a
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	22 de	13 a	6.3 bc	36 a
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	121 bc	19 a	3.3 a	5 b
<i>Cyperus diffusus</i>	112 bc	26 b	4.7 abc	3 b
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (sorghum)	60 bcd	15 a	11.7 d	7 b
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	36 bcde	26 b	6.7 c	3 b
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	97 bc	25 ^c	5.0 ^d	1 b
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	14 ef	15 ^c	5.0 ^d	5 b
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	161 ab	^e		
<i>Rottboellia exaltata</i>	140 bc	^e		
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	136 abc	^e		
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	82 bcd	^e		
<i>Panicum repens</i>	53 bcde	^e		
<i>Zea mays</i> (maize)	52 bcde	^e		
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	45 de	^e		
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	30 cde	^e		
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i>	9 fg	^e		
<i>Cyperus diffusus</i>	2 g	^e		

^aVegetative-stage plants were used. Av of 3 replications, 1 moth pair/cage (replication). In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$). ^bNo-choice test as one plant species/cage. ^cLarval development attained in one replication only; not included in statistical analysis. ^dPupal development obtained only in one out of 3 replications; not included in statistical analysis. ^eLarvae died during first instar.

glabrescens, *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Panicum repens*, *Rottboellia exaltata*, *Imperata cylindrica*, *Commelina diffusa*,

Paspalidium flavidum, *Cyperus rotundus*, and maize. □

Influence of weather on populations of rice white leafhopper in light traps

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A modified Robinson's light trap with a 125-W mercury vapor lamp was used to trap white leafhopper (WL) *Cofana spectra* (Distant) at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, for 15 mo. Daily number of trapped WL was recorded as well as maximum and minimum temperature, relative humidity, and total rainfall. There was a highly significant negative

Association between light trap population of *C. spectra* and minimum temperature and rainfall. Light trap population represents total adults trapped in 4 wk.

Table 1. Relation between light trap catches of *C. spectra* and weather factors.

Weather factor	r value ^a
Max temp	-0.179
Min temp	-0.628**
Relative humidity	-0.147
Total rainfall	-0.270*

^a*Significant at 5% level, **significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Partial regression coefficients, standard error and proportional contribution of weather factors to regression of light trap population of *C. spectra*.

Weather factor	Partial regression coefficient	Standard error	Proportional contribution to R ² (%)
Max temp	-7.816	6.468	2.42
Min temp	-26.365**	4.960	36.16
Relative humidity	-4.558	3.183	2.34
Total rainfall	-0.575	0.560	3.17

Constant term 'a' = 1305.255, R² = 0.4411. **Significant at 1% level.

relation ($r = -0.628^{**}$ between minimum temperature and WL population (Table 1, figure). A significant negative relation ($r = -0.27^{*}$) existed between total rain-

fall and WL population.

The partial regression coefficient and the proportional contribution of the different weather factors on the light trap

WL population are in Table 2. Minimum temperature affected WL population most. □

Parasitization of gall midge by *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi)

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Rice gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) was heavily parasitized by two chalcid parasites — *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi) and *Platygaster oryzae* (Cameron) — in the GM-endemic area, College of Agriculture, Raipur, during 1981 kharif.

Parasitization ranged from 21 to 94% when 75 midges were observed each day in Oct and Nov. *N. grallarius* (Hymenoptera: Eupelmidae) parasitized GM pupae 1 mo earlier than *P. oryzae* and was pre-

Parasitism of chalcids on rice gall midge, Raipur, India.

sent through the third week of Nov, peaking at 75% parasitism (see figure). This is the first record of heavy parasitization of GM by *N. grallarius* in India. □

Complete slide sets of photos printed in *Field problems of tropical rice*, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Pest management and control NEMATODES

Nursery application of carbofuran for control of rice root nematode

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Rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* causes substantial economic losses in lowland rice areas. The nematode damages the crop in the nursery and in the field. In 1981-82 samba we compared a nursery application of carbofuran 3% G broadcast at 1.275 kg ai/ha for control of rice root nematode with an untreated plot in a randomized block design with 16 replications in Panayapuram and Rachandarthirumalai villages of Tiruchi, Tamil Nadu.

Ponni and IR20 were planted in 3.75- × 2.5-m flooded plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Ponni was transplanted at 40 d and IR20 at 30 d. Carbofuran was applied 7 d before transplanting. Root samples were collected from the nursery by pull-

Rice root nematode population^a and grain yield after carbofuran application, Tiruchi, India.^b

Treatment	Nematode population/5-g root						Grain yield/plot (kg)
	Nursery		Days after transplanting			Before harvest	
	Before treatment	7 DAT ^c	15	30	60		
<i>Panayapuram</i>							
Carbofuran 3% G, 1.275 kg ai/ha	11.09	0.70	5.67	7.26	12.50	14.43	7.5
Untreated control	11.23	13.91	14.30	16.44	14.82	15.00	6.9
<i>Rachandarthirumalai</i>							
Carbofuran 3% G, 1.275 kg ai/ha	6.39	0.70	3.69	6.02	12.90	15.90	4.6
Untreated control	6.18	7.14	8.51	13.53	14.98	16.43	4.4
C. D. for population, 2.66		C. D. for yield, 0.196					

^aTransformed values. ^bMean for 16 replications. ^cDays after treatment.

ing 10 plants, at random, before pesticide application and at transplanting. Samples were taken from the field 15, 30, and 60 d after transplanting and just before harvest.

Nematode population was estimated by the Baermann pan technique using 5 g root/sample. The nematode population

data were analyzed after $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformation. Grain yield was recorded. Results of the pooled analysis of infestation and yield are in the table.

Carbofuran application significantly reduced the rice root nematode population in the nursery and up to 30 d after transplanting. □